

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF COMPETENCIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIASAVODKHANISM IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article provides insights into media, media competence in the era of modern globalization. Also, the mechanisms for the formation of media competencies, which should be developed in them for the correct use of the media in future doctors, are outlined in the article.*

Keywords: *information, media, students, media competence, mediate education, competence, skills, doctors.*

Introduction. Globalization in the world, rapidly developing processes of digitalization, political, economic, ideological conflicts of interest increase the informational and psychological impact of the media, causing the process of struggle for the consciousness of people to increase. The increased interest of young people in the media flow of information, the relevance of the problem of information security and cybersecurity, the reduction of commercial functions of information as a commodity, pollution of the information environment, the emergence of various forms of inappropriate information in IT, media dependence dictate the formation of students' mediaeval competencies to regulate the relationship of young people. According to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 "on the approval of the strategy" digital Uzbekistan-2030" and measures for its effective implementation "PF-6079", comprehensive measures for the active development of the digital economy in our country, the widespread introduction of modern communication technologies in all sectors and areas, first of all In order to ensure the implementation of this decree, it will be necessary for students of higher education institutions to comprehensively master innovative education, information and communication technologies and digital technologies in their field of knowledge, modern professional development and improvement of their professional training, a good understanding of the goals and objectives of this process. Media in modern information society, media education, the use of media in educational processes, the public ax of a modern future doctor.

Research Methodology. Why is it important for students to be mediocre? Today, media competence remains the most necessary skill for young people of the 21st century. Just like the ability to read, write, this is a very important skill. The reason is, today people live in the media world, using different sources of information. Of course, everyone should think for themselves how useful or harmful this information can be. In this Sense, media information can be understood as a metaphor comparable to food. Normally, the food that is nauseous. Eating a food that is too fatty or too spicy is bad for the body. Of course, in this matter a person needs to decide what he will choose. The information is the same. Products of different tastes can be selected, but it is not necessary to have the same, that is, to have unnecessary information, read them, eat them. In our opinion, this metaphor perfectly demonstrates what is happening now in the information world. Everything like Fast fud (fast cooking dish) Based on the topic of our research, what is the Media itself before covering the issue of the development of media competencies in future doctors? What

is media competence? What is media competence? Why is it important to develop media competence in future doctors? Let's well on such important questions as one of the main Fists of mankind from the first moments of its appearance is the exchange of information, that is, the first gesture with each other, and later the exchange of information through speech after the development of speech. It follows from this that from the very beginning of the emergence of mankind, has been living with the media. In our study, we will get acquainted with the basics of media and media competence. That is, what the media is cannot be explained by a two-word sentence, it is a very comprehensive concept. There is a lot of speculation about when the Media came into existence. If, from his rule, it is who gave the first information to mankind in history. First stage. In the structure of the primitive community, people painted the first images on stones using the example of an inscription or a picture, and the scrolls and pictures on this stone today help us a lot in the study of history. The scrolls on the Stones continued to write on human skin until the invention of paper. Representatives who came out of the community conveyed historical events, various collective holidays, historical dates, addresses where their tribe was located, by writing scrolls to each other in stone. These historical Scrolls, books written on the skin of haivans some of them have come down to us and are preserved in famous museums around the world today.

Conclusion. Media is a system of correct and circular communicative communication in society, a space that creates temporary interaction with people and interests them, distracting them. The term "Media" - in the 20th century-originally applied to media that shape mass culture [4, 223]. As described in the documents of the European Union, mediata education – (media edusion) is an education aimed at developing mediasavodkhanism, which should be understood as a critical and thoughtful attitude to the media in order to educate responsible citizens who are able to express their opinion on the basis of the information received. It is the use of the necessary information to students, its analysis, identification of the economic, social and cultural interests associated with them.

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